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Abstract

This document presents the project's results and outcomes to EU policy makers. In addition, it outlines the project's connections with other Research Infrastructures and the EOSC community, ensuring its findings can support future policy and programme developments.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Research software is a foundational component of science, critical for Europe's research leadership, innovation, and public investment impact. Despite its importance, the quality and sustainability of research software are not systematically supported, risking reproducibility, efficiency, and competitiveness at global level.

The EVERSE project seeks to address these gaps by providing a common European reference for good practices, recognition, and professionalization in research software.

Key recommendations include:

1. It is essential to establish and maintain a common **European knowledge base for good practices on research software** for the communities and driven by the communities.
2. We must establish and adopt a **common definition of research software quality**, building on the common perception of research software quality and its **indicators** across domains.
3. We must **recognize and reward contributions** in research software and establish effective distribution of credit to Research Software Engineering professionals and its **recognition** by their employers.
4. We must **establish and support capacity-building activities** to consolidate the professionalism of the European practitioners in the research software field.
5. We must **capitalize on the research software capacities** within Europe and develop a resilient, robust and **independent research software ecosystem** and recognize its value as a **European asset**

The EVERSE project provides a comprehensive roadmap to enhance research software quality, professionalize RSEs, and consolidate Europe's leadership in scientific software. Through community-driven initiatives, standards, and capacity-building, EVERSE aims to transform research software into a recognized, sustainable, and strategic asset for the European Research Area.

Ultimately, effective implementation requires engagement from publishers, educators, and graduate programs, adoption of mandatory software quality statements, and incentivization through badging or certification. EVERSE supports alignment of policy, standards, and recognition mechanisms across Europe to embed research software quality into the scientific system.

1 Introduction

Strong, sustainable research software is essential to protect Europe's global research leadership and ensure public investments deliver maximum impact. To this end, research software is a critical infrastructure for Europe's knowledge economy. Strengthening its quality and sustainability advances digital sovereignty, secures competitiveness, and bolsters the innovation goals of the European Research Area. Research software underpins the majority of modern scientific discoveries, yet its quality and sustainability are not systematically supported. To safeguard reproducibility, maximize the impact of public investment, and maintain Europe's global leadership in research and innovation, dedicated action on research software quality is essential. Public investment in research depends increasingly on software that is robust, sustainable, and trustworthy. Strengthening research software quality is therefore critical to maximizing returns on Europe's scientific and technological leadership.

The [ReSA/RDA FAIR for Research Software Working Group](#) defines research software as “*source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose.*”¹ single use analysis developed by a “researcher who codes” for their immediate needs and to foundational and widely used software developed by Research Software Engineer (RSE) professionals who combines expertise in software development with a deep understanding of research practices.

The EVERSE project aims to become a common European reference point for good practices in research software, driven by community engagement. It is essential to adopt a shared definition of research software quality, along with recognized indicators across domains, to maintain and build upon past investments while addressing reproducibility, maintainability, security, code mobility, and green computing challenges. Recognizing and rewarding contributions in research software is equally crucial for formalizing the role of [Research Software Engineers \(RSEs\)](#) and supporting capacity-building efforts to professionalize the field. In addition, strengthening community-building efforts and bridging diverse groups, which include the wider community of researchers who code to the more formal RSE societies (SocRSE, RSE.de), and initiatives (Carpentries, Research Software Alliance) will further reinforce collaboration. Ultimately, EVERSE seeks to leverage Europe's research software capacity to develop a resilient, independent, and strategically valuable ecosystem, fostering diversity while encouraging convergence to maximize return on investment and global competitiveness.

This document provides an initial set of clear and actionable recommendations that directly stem from the collective experience, expertise and efforts of the EVERSE project members.

¹ Gruenpeter, M., Katz, D. S., Lamprecht, A.-L., Honeyman, T., Garijo, D., Struck, A., Niehues, A., Martinez, P. A., Castro, L. J., Rabemanantsoa, T., Chue Hong, N. P., Martinez-Ortiz, C., Sesink, L., Liffers, M., Fouilloux, A. C., Erdmann, C., Peroni, S., Martinez Lavanchy, P., Todorov, I., & Sinha, M. (2021). *Defining Research Software: a controversial discussion (Version 1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5504016>

2 Actionable recommendations

It is essential to establish and maintain a common European **knowledge base for good practices on research software** for the communities and driven by the communities.

Building a common European knowledge base for research software good practices is like constructing a shared library for a community of builders. Instead of each builder individually rediscovering the best ways to lay foundations or erect walls, they can contribute their proven techniques and learn from others' experiences, creating a collective wisdom that ensures consistently high-quality structures for everyone.

The Research Software Quality toolkit (RSQKit): The EVERSE project proposes RSQKit as a knowledge hub to gather and curate expertise around developing and improving research software quality. It brings together communities' best practices and provides mechanisms for researchers to access this knowledge at different stages of their software development journey. The RSQKit is envisioned as a gateway to catalogues and services related to research software quality, as well as an online resource for standards and best practices, potentially integrating with the overall European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. This RSQKit is seen as a major contribution to the EOSC ecosystem.

We must establish and adopt a **common definition of research software quality**, building on the common perception of research software quality and its **indicators** across domains.

Defining a common standard for research software quality is like standardizing the units of measurement in science. Just as physicists around the world agree on what a "metre" is, or chemists on what a "mole" is, establishing a common definition of "quality" for research software, along with agreed-upon indicators, allows researchers across different disciplines and countries to build, share, and evaluate research software using a shared understanding, ensuring consistency and trustworthiness in scientific outputs.

Establishing a Common Understanding of Quality: The EVERSE project explicitly aims to define the notion of software quality in the context of EOSC, drawing upon established practices by the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles and other communities. This aligns with the ambition for widespread acceptance across EOSC Science Clusters and the broader research community regarding minimum quality indicators.

Consolidating Quality Indicators: A core objective of EVERSE is to leverage existing tools and resources to support the evaluation, verification, and improvement of research software and code quality, based on existing practices and standards across research communities. Specifically, EVERSE will define baseline quality indicators for research software quality, based on a common framework of best practices, aiming for wider application across various digital objects like software, code, workflows, and models. These indicators are envisioned to be "fit for purpose" and are structured around a three-tier model for research software (analysis code, prototype tools, and research software

infrastructure).

We must **recognize and reward contributions** in research **software** and establish effective distribution of credit to Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and its recognition by their employers.

The increasing prevalence of coding in scientific practice contrasts starkly with the lack of training that most researchers receive in software development. A significant concern among Research Infrastructures (RIs) within the EOSC Science Clusters is that researchers who specialise in software and computing frequently miss out on academic career development opportunities and rewards. This issue is considered critical because increasingly scientific success depends on these specialist researchers. For early-career researchers involved in relevant software activities, their work must be acknowledged as first-class scientific activities. The EVERSE project aims to bring about permanent change to this situation. This aligns with Science Europe's broader objective to improve the recognition of research software development for scholarly careers.

Development of a Credit and Policy Framework: EVERSE will actively contribute to developing a credit system and a policy framework for rewarding researchers and professional RSEs committed to Open Science practices and involved in research or training activities. This initiative will build upon existing efforts, such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) commitments, the Research Software Alliance's (ReSA) task force on software policy, and the Amsterdam Declaration on Research Software (ADORE.software).

Community-Driven Recognition and Career Progression: The project emphasizes fostering a community where contributions are recognized and credited. EVERSE aims to build a collaborative, community-led structure for evaluating and improving research software quality, creating a foundation for a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence that enables an organisational and policy framework. By demonstrating improvements in research software quality and maximizing its reuse, EVERSE will drive the recognition of software and support career progression for developers, including researchers who code and RSEs. The success of pilot cases is expected to encourage broader adoption of EVERSE practices, which in turn promote recognition.

We must **establish and support capacity-building activities** to consolidate the professionalism of the European practitioners in the research software field.

Supporting capacity-building activities for research software practitioners is like investing in a specialized academy for skilled artisans. Just as an academy nurtures talent, refines techniques, and provides formal qualifications to elevate the craft to a recognized profession, these initiatives aim to equip RSEs with the necessary skills, knowledge, and formal recognition, transforming their crucial contributions into a respected and sustainable career path within the scientific landscape.

Addressing a Cultural Gap and Career Development:

A key barrier to research software excellence in RIs across the EOSC Science Clusters is the limited training and

career development pathways available to specialists in software and computing. Despite their crucial role in enabling modern scientific breakthroughs, these researchers often receive little recognition or reward within academic structures. The EVERSE project tackles this challenge by prioritizing training and capacity building initiatives that empower early-career researchers to develop strong professional profiles and gain visibility for their contributions. By embedding these activities into the research ecosystem, EVERSE seeks to establish software development as a fully recognized and valued scientific endeavor, in line with Science Europe's vision for strengthening scholarly careers in this field. **Mechanisms for Skills Development and Knowledge Sharing:** EVERSE collects, enhances, and curates training resources aligned with domain-specific practices, creating a long-term training activity supported by community services and platforms. Moreover, the RSQKit serves as a knowledge hub to gather and curate expertise, offering guidelines, tools, services, and training materials. This toolkit provides researchers with actionable indicators and metrics for software quality throughout their development journey. Ultimately, the long-term training activities provided through the project will facilitate the consolidation of good practices and provide researchers with the knowledge and skills needed to succeed in their careers.

We must **capitalize on the research software capacities** within Europe and develop a resilient, robust and **independent research software ecosystem** and recognize its value as a **European asset**

This comprehensive approach views research software not merely as a tool, but as a fundamental pillar of European scientific and innovation capacity, requiring deliberate investment and strategic development. It's like nurturing a highly skilled workforce in a cutting-edge industry: by investing in their training, tools, and recognition, and integrating their efforts across the continent, Europe aims to ensure a self-sufficient and pioneering lead in the global scientific landscape.

Capitalizing on Existing Research Software Capacities: Europe possesses numerous software applications that are essential to scientific research. The strategy involves building on these existing strengths and the expertise held across the continent. Key elements include:

- Leveraging expertise from leading national Research Software Expertise Centres such as SSI, NLeSC, and HIFIS, which specialise in research software practices.
- Harnessing the contributions of the five EOSC Science Clusters, which actively develop and manage research software for diverse European communities in fields like astro and particle physics, life sciences, photon and neutron science, environmental science, and social sciences and humanities.
- Utilising the established services and deep expertise in data management and analysis brought by European RIs, which demonstrated their capacity during the COVID-19 pandemic response and have the potential to host knowledge and new services long-term.
- Actively engaging individual researchers and national Open Science efforts within the broader EOSC ecosystem who already play active roles in shaping the landscape.
- Building on existing good practices and resources to develop and consolidate new policies.

Recognizing its Value as a European Asset: Research software is increasingly acknowledged as a vital strategic asset for Europe's scientific progress and innovation capacity:

- It is considered an **“integral part of scientific endeavour”**, particularly critical for data-driven domains.
- Improving the quality and organisation of research software **accelerates research and innovation**.
- A better organised research software landscape across Europe will **“bring the fruits of new technical innovations to the benefit of the society within the EU and beyond”** more effectively and rapidly. This highlights its strategic importance for societal and economic advancement.
- The goal is for research software to be recognised as a **“first-class citizen of the scientific process”**, with its contributors properly credited for their efforts.
- Higher quality and more sustainable research software leads to **more efficient use of financial, computational, and human resources**, demonstrating its economic value.
- Research Infrastructures are identified as **crucial enablers of research and technological innovation** and drivers of multidisciplinary and data-intensive science.
- The EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda ([SRIA](#)) explicitly aims to **“Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code”** and to mainstream Open Science skills, reinforcing the strategic importance of this asset.

3 Policy outcomes and implications

These recommendations could potentially drive the following changes:

A common European knowledge base for good practices on research software driven by science communities:

The policy aims to establish a **common European knowledge base** for good practices in research software. This is envisioned through initiatives like the **Research Software Quality toolkit (RSQKit)** within the EVERSE project. RSQKit is intended to be a **community-driven, living knowledge hub** for researchers, curating and aggregating content from EOSC Science Clusters and external Research Software Expertise Centres. It will provide **guidelines, tools, and services** for high-quality software across disciplines. The objective is to foster alignment of existing initiatives by **promoting coherence and developing community guidelines**. The context highlights the urgent need for a more robust policy framework for research software, especially due to the impact of new technologies like Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) and Quantum Computing on research. Science Europe supports organisations in building this framework as part of their **open science strategies**, emphasizing shared responsibility with other research actors.

To embed research software quality into the scientific system, engagement from publishers, educators, and training programs is essential. Journals and publishing entities can lead by requiring mandatory “software quality statements”, similar to data availability statements, and by adopting badging or certification schemes that recognize reproducible and FAIR-compliant software. To this end, graduate programs should include courses in Research Software Engineering (RSE), a standard component of PhD or Postdoc training especially in computational fields, equipping researchers not only with coding skills but with the ability to produce robust, trustworthy software for science. Similarly, the development of authoritative textbooks and training resources would provide a common reference point across disciplines, ensuring that principles of testing, reproducibility, and sustainability are widely taught.

Adoption of a common definition of research software quality, building on common perception and indicators across multiple scientific domains:

The goal would be for the key stakeholders in the European Ecosystem (such as the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), European Intergovernmental Research Organisation forum (EIROforum), European Commission (EC) etc) to adopt a **common definition of research software quality** based on shared perceptions and indicators across various science clusters (e.g., ENVRI-FAIR, PaNOSC, ESCAPE, SSHOC, LifeScience-RI). Science Europe recommends² that organisations **provide a clear definition of ‘research software’** and other key terms (e.g., sustainability, accessibility, usability) to clarify policy scope. The EVERSE project directly addresses this by defining a **baseline of Source Code quality** based on coding principles and good practices in different research communities. It will leverage and extend **measurable indicators for research software and code quality**, including code maturity, considering the concept of “**fit for purpose**”. The project distinguishes between “metrics” and “indicators”, preferring

² Saenen, B. (2025). *Developing and Aligning Policies on Research Software: Recommendations for Research Funding and Research Performing Organisations*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14622355>

“indicators” for a **more holistic view of software quality**, encompassing quantitative and qualitative measures, user satisfaction, and community engagement. This common framework will build on existing efforts such as FAIR research software frameworks, workflow frameworks, and initiatives for minimum metadata and quality for models. The aim is a **universally adopted framework** for measuring quality and FAIRness, aligning with international standards.

Recognition and reward for contributions in research software towards formal accreditation of RSE professionals:

The policy aims to **recognize and reward contributions in research software** to build towards a formal accreditation of the Research Software Engineer (RSE) professional. Improving the **recognition of research software development for scholarly careers** is a key element of the broader research landscape context. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) commitments are specifically relevant for this. The EVERSE project explicitly states that **credit and recognition for developers and software are essential** for promoting sustainable software practices. A primary objective of EVERSE is to provide a framework for appropriate **recognition, reward, and career development** for researchers and RSEs who implement quality assurance practices. This includes creating a **formal recognition system**³ and opportunities for rewards to acknowledge their contributions and provide clear career paths. This initiative builds on existing efforts like CoARA, the Research Software Alliance's task force on software policy, and the Amsterdam Declaration on Research Software. The goal is to bring about a **cultural change in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)** to enhance career prospects and rewarding mechanisms for RSEs and researchers who code.

Support for capacity-building activities to consolidate professionalism in the European Research Software field:

The policy advocates for supporting **capacity-building activities** to strengthen the professionalism of European practitioners in the research software field. In the broader research landscape, placing research software effectively involves **offering training programmes**. The EVERSE project aims to foster a collaborative community to guarantee research software quality and explicitly includes **training for researchers, RSEs, and other stakeholders** as a key result. EVERSE will deliver expertise through a comprehensive **training programme**, considering domain-specific needs and the three-tier model for research software. A dedicated effort under EVERSE is towards “**Capacity building and recognition**”, providing training, guidance, and education to enhance understanding of software quality and application of best practices. This includes developing and aligning existing training materials for software development skills and digital badges. Long-term training activities are planned, supported by community services and platforms.

Capitalizing on European Research Software capacities to develop a resilient, robust, and independent research software ecosystem and recognizing its value as a European asset:

This policy emphasizes **capitalizing on existing European research software capacities** to foster a resilient, robust, and independent research software ecosystem, acknowledging its value as a European asset. Science Europe

³ Vergoulis, T., Maria Makaronidou, Amodeo, S., Stavropoulos, T., Quaglia, F., Bouhraoua, K. E. A., Roiser, S., Garijo, D., Piovesan, D., Psomopoulos, F., Pechlivanis, N., Orfanou, A., & Bakoglidou, E. (2025). D5.1 Landscape analysis of existing rewards and mechanisms for research software and training activities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14978474>

supports organisations⁴ in building a **more robust policy framework for research software** as a strategic part of Open Science. They highlight the **joint effort and shared responsibility** among various research actors to support infrastructure development and integrate research software into the broader research landscape. The vision is for the European Research Area to have **optimal conditions** for robust education and research & innovation systems, championing best practices. The EVERSE project's overarching ambition is to **accelerate research and innovation by improving research software quality**. It aims to ensure research software is recognized as an integral part of scientific endeavour, leading to better access, management, interoperability, and reuse through EOSC resources. A core goal of EVERSE is to **build the foundation for a sustainable Virtual Institute** dedicated to improving software excellence, increasing reliability and sustainability, and fostering community collaboration. The project asserts that **better organisation of research software across Europe** will accelerate the benefits of technical innovations for society. It aims to establish a European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence, engaging science communities, and connecting with international organisations and industry.

⁴ Saenen, B. (2025). *Developing and Aligning Policies on Research Software: Recommendations for Research Funding and Research Performing Organisations*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14622355>